

Graph Neural Network Architecture for MIMO Channel Estimation

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Abstract—Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are gaining popularity to solve wireless communication problems due to the inherent nature of viewing wireless networks as graphs. In this paper, we investigate the potential of using GNN for channel estimation in point-to-point multi-input and multi-output (MIMO) systems. The analysis includes an assessment of the channel estimation error performance, alongside the computational complexity associated to the training and inference phases. The performance is compared against benchmarks such as the conventional least squares, (linear) MMSE estimators, and shallow 1D convolutional neural network (1D-CNN) architectures from the literature. We evaluate the performance-complexity trade-off of GNN versus shallow 1D-CNN which have been shown to outperform deep architectures for MIMO channel estimation.

Index Terms—Graph Neural Network, Convolutional Neural Network, MIMO, Channel Estimation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In massive Multi-Input and Multi-Output (mMIMO) systems, acquiring reliable channel state information (CSI) is highly important for the performance of many signal-processing blocks. Sub-optimal (linear) schemes used for this task include linear least-squares (LS) and minimum mean squared error (MMSE) estimation schemes, among others. Alternatively, machine learning (ML) approaches can not only be leveraged to learn non-linear features of the transmission environment, but also to achieve better performance under non-Gaussian environments or model uncertainties, at the expense of additional computational complexity. As an alternative to Deep Neural Network (DNN) or Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) [1], [2], this paper investigates the potential of Graph Neural Network (GNN) for the task of channel estimation.

The inherent nature of viewing wireless network as graphs has paved way for the application of GNN in various tasks such as beamforming, power control, channel decoding [3], [4]. GNNs are shown to be scalable architectures requiring lesser number of trainable parameters than DNN and CNN. Specifically addressing channel estimation, there are a range of ML tools used for this task. The survey [5] covers a collection of deep learning (DL) based estimators that are designed to refine the output of conventional estimators. These DL approaches (for both symbol-by-symbol and frame-by-frame

estimators) take as input a coarse channel estimate which is derived from conventional estimators (like spectral temporal averaging, data-pilot aided). In a similar manner, [6] employs GNN to map an initial channel estimate to the actual channel.

Unlike [5], [6], the approach presented in this paper *directly* works on the received pilot signals, which is in line with our previous work [7]. Shallow architectures of 1D-CNNs were found to offer reliable channel estimation performance at a reduced computational complexity than shallow/deep DNNs and 2D-CNNs. The reshaping of the received signals into various formats showed a drastic change in the number of trainable parameters and computational complexity in the inference phase. The input to the CNNs [8] include the real, imaginary, and modulus values of the received signal, while the DNNs operate on stacked vectors [7], or separately process the real and imaginary parts [9]. In B5G/6G edge networks, compact neural network models are crucial in determining the computational overhead introduced by ML, both in the training and inference phases.

In [10], channel estimation is carried out with graph attention network (GAT), shown to be robust against changes in channel parameters. But the usage of GAT in full-duplex communication scenario, does not exploit the graph nature of the wireless network. The real and imaginary parts of the received signal are viewed as node attributes, while the edge attributes are set as the received pilot symbols. On the contrary, in our proposed GNN model, the edges represent the MIMO channel to be estimated. We use a bipartite graph to represent transmit and receiver nodes, where the latter store the received pilot signals. The message passing algorithm (MPA) on the underlying graph structure aids the task of channel estimation.

As 1D-CNN architectures have been shown to be the most computationally efficient choice among the neural networks to perform channel estimation [7] at the receiver, this paper analyzes the performance-complexity trade-off of GNN versus 1D-CNN. Unlike [6], [10], the proposed GNN works directly on the graph topology of the wireless network to estimate the MIMO channel. We study the computational complexity in the *training* phase with respect to the number of trainable parameters employed, and the size of training dataset required to reach convergence. The complexity in *inference* phase is analyzed by looking into the number of operations (multiplications/additions) performed by the neural network schemes compared with linear benchmarks.

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II. SIGNAL MODEL AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

We consider a point-to-point MIMO system where the transmitter and the receiver are equipped with N_T and N_R antennas, respectively. The received signal corresponding to the transmission of N_P pilot symbols can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{N} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_P}$, $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_T}$ is the channel matrix, $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N_P}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T \times N_P}$ denotes the unit modulus transmit QPSK signals, and $\mathbf{N} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_P}$ represents the zero-mean i.i.d. additive Gaussian white noise of variance σ^2 . We model the channel as a random matrix with separable covariance, resulting in $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{C}_{\text{Rx}}^{1/2} \mathbf{G} \mathbf{C}_{\text{Tx}}^{1/2}$, where the entries of the matrix \mathbf{G} are modeled as i.i.d. circularly symmetric Gaussian-distributed with zero mean and unit variance, with \mathbf{C}_{Tx} and \mathbf{C}_{Rx} denoting the transmit and receive covariance matrices, respectively.

In conventional channel estimation, the Least-Squares (LS) scheme computes the channel estimate as

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{LS}} = \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{X}^H (\mathbf{X}\mathbf{X}^H)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

The Minimum Mean Squared Error (MMSE) channel estimator with knowledge of the spatial correlation matrices is the optimal estimator for the considered setting in terms of MSE. After some algebra [11], the estimate can be computed as

$$\text{vec}(\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{MMSE}}) = (\mathbf{C}_{\text{Tx}}^T \mathbf{X}^* \otimes \mathbf{C}_{\text{Rx}}) \times \left[(\mathbf{X}^H \mathbf{C}_{\text{Tx}} \mathbf{X})^T \otimes \mathbf{C}_{\text{Rx}} + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_R N_P} \right]^{-1} \text{vec}(\mathbf{Y}) \quad (3)$$

where \otimes denotes Kronecker product and where the $\text{vec}()$ operator stacks the columns of a matrix on top of one another. The implementation of the optimum channel estimator requires perfect knowledge of the channel covariance matrices. They are typically unknown and cannot be represented in closed-form [12], the relevant iterative methods are computationally intensive. For this reason, it is quite common to consider the MMSE under the assumption of uncorrelated channel matrix entries, which takes the form

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{u-MMSE}} = \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{X}^H (\mathbf{X}\mathbf{X}^H + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_R})^{-1} \quad (4)$$

where subindex ‘‘u’’ is used to denote the uncorrelation assumption.

III. NEURAL NETWORK-BASED CHANNEL ESTIMATION

Channel estimation can be modelled as a supervised learning problem. The training dataset comprises a total of M examples of the received signal $\mathbf{y}^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2N_R N_P \times 1}$ and labels $\mathbf{h}^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2N_R N_T \times 1}$, ($m = 1, \dots, M$). The training procedure consists of the following steps:

- 1) Generation of the received signal for a total of M realizations of the communication scenario. For each channel realization, N_P pilot symbols and noise vectors are generated.
- 2) Letting the label of each example to be the actual channel impulse response.

Fig. 1. 1D-CNN for channel estimation.

Channel estimation is viewed as a multi-output regression task where:

- The input of the NNs is given by $\mathbf{y} = \text{vec}[\text{Re}(\mathbf{Y}) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\mathbf{Y}) \otimes [0, 1]]$. The vector \mathbf{y} is reshaped into different formats depending on the actual architecture of the neural network used.
- The output of all the NNs is the actual channel response $\mathbf{h} = \text{vec}[\text{Re}(\mathbf{H}) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\mathbf{H}) \otimes [0, 1]]$.

The next subsections describe (i) 1D-CNN based channel estimation, and (ii) GNN-based learning schemes considered in this work.

A. 1D Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN)

In 1D-CNN, the trainable weights are arranged in 2-D kernels for convolution operations. These kernels slide in *one* direction only (e.g., along the time axis) to produce feature maps. The pilot symbols sent from the transmitter can be viewed as a time-series, thus advocating the use of 1D-CNN for channel estimation (refer to our previous work [7], for details). As shown in Figure 1, there are as many feature maps as the number of kernels N_k in the convolutional layer. The feature maps are then flattened and connected to the output layer.

Each of the kernels ($1 \dots N_k$) is denoted by $\mathbf{K}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{k_h \times k_w}$, where k_h and k_w stand for the kernel height and width, respectively. The kernel convolves on the input (or previous feature map) $\mathbf{Y}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{h_l \times w_l}$, where h_l and w_l denote its height and width. The generated output feature map $\mathbf{Z}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times (w_l - k_w + 1)}$ can thus be expressed as

$$(\mathbf{Z}_l)_n = \sum_{i=1}^{k_h} \sum_{j=1}^{k_w} (\mathbf{K}_l)_{i,j} (\mathbf{Y}_l)_{i,j+n-1} \quad (5)$$

The training of CNN model involves identifying the optimal kernel weights for the regression task.

B. Graph Neural Network (GNN)

The proposed solution considers Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) that learn hidden representation of the edges in a graph. For MIMO channel estimation, the edges between the transmit and receive antennas represent the wireless channel. A bipartite graph is defined as $\mathcal{G} = ((\mathcal{V}_s, \mathcal{V}_t), \mathcal{E})$, where \mathcal{V}_s is the set of source nodes (transmit antennas) while \mathcal{V}_t is the set of target nodes (receive antennas). The set $\mathcal{V} = (\mathcal{V}_s, \mathcal{V}_t)$ contains

all transmit and receive nodes. \mathcal{E} contains all edges between the transmit and receive antennas i.e., $(t, r) \in \mathcal{E} \forall t, r \in \mathcal{V}$. The graph is undirected, $(t, r) \in \mathcal{E} \iff (r, t) \in \mathcal{E}$, similar to the physical channel between transmitter and receiver.

The N_T transmit and N_R receiver antennas are viewed as nodes of a bipartite graph, while the edges of the graph represent the MIMO channel, with $N_E = N_T \cdot N_R$ being the total number of edges of the graph. The L -layer GNN consists of: (i) one input layer depicting the wireless network as a graph with each of the receiver nodes (Rx Nodes) containing the received signals at the antenna, i.e., $2N_P$ elements (the real and imaginary parts of the received pilots); (ii) one output layer with each of the edges holding the estimated channel coefficients; and (iii) $L - 2$ hidden layers with $d_l (l = 2, \dots, L - 2)$ edge features each.

The first hidden layer computes the edge features that represent the initial estimate of the channel coefficients. In the subsequent hidden layers of the GNN, we make use of edge-GNN [13] that learn edge embeddings over each hidden layer. The mechanism of the message passing algorithm (MPA) in the l -th hidden layer¹ is shown in Figure 2, and described next.

Fig. 2. GNN for channel estimation, visualized for a single edge $(0,0)$ in the graph. The message passing operations are shown in (a) message aggregation at receive nodes $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}$ and (b) message aggregation at transmit nodes $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}$, while (c) shows the updated edge feature as per update rule (6).

Message Passing Algorithm (MPA): The embedding of each edge (t, r) in layer l is represented as $z_{(t,r)}^l$ which holds the real and imaginary coefficients of the channel along the particular edge i.e., $z_{(t,r)}^l = [\text{Re}(h_{t,r}), \text{Im}(h_{t,r})]^T$. In each of the hidden layers, the operations consist of message-passing iterations and an update step, which is expressed as below

$$\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l+1)} = \text{UPDATE}^{(l)} \left(\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}$ and $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}$ are the messages aggregated from the neighboring nodes of edge (t, r) , which is defined as

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)} = \text{AGGREGATE}^{(l)} \left(\left\{ \mathbf{z}_{(t,x)}^{(l)}, \forall x \in \mathcal{N}(t) \right\} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)} = \text{AGGREGATE}^{(l)} \left(\left\{ \mathbf{z}_{(x,r)}^{(l)}, \forall x \in \mathcal{N}(r) \right\} \right) \quad (8)$$

It should be noted that the UPDATE and AGGREGATE are differentiable functions [13] that need to be defined.

¹Each of the hidden layers corresponds to one round of iterations of the Message Passing Algorithm.

The update rule in (6) can be expanded as below

$$\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l+1)} = \text{UPDATE}^{(l)} \left(\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$= \sigma \left(W_{\text{edge}}^{(l)} \mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l)} + W_t^{(l)} \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)} + W_r^{(l)} \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l+1)}$ denotes the hidden representation of the edge (t, r) at the $(l+1)$ layer of the GNN, $\sigma(\cdot)$ is a non-linear activation function and the matrices $W_{\text{edge}}^{(l)}, W_t^{(l)}, W_r^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{l+1} \times d_l}$ are learnt using stochastic gradient descent. In this work, Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) are used as activation functions in all hidden layers. At the output layer, a linear activation function is used to compute the values of the elements of the channel matrix.

Similar to [4], [14], we define the message *aggregation* (via the AGGREGATE function in Equation (7), and (8)) passed between the nodes as follows

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}(t)|} \sum_{r' \in \mathcal{N}(t)} \mathbf{z}_{(t,r')}^{(l)} \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}(r)|} \sum_{t' \in \mathcal{N}(r)} \mathbf{z}_{(t',r)}^{(l)} \quad (12)$$

The dimensions of these matrices, d_{l+1} and d_l , determine the number of features in layers $(l+1)$ and l , respectively. For the MIMO channel estimation problem, the output layer of GNN has $d_o = 2$ features on each edge, to account for the number of real and imaginary parts of the channel matrix. The optimum edge features d_l of the hidden layers is found via hyperparameter tuning. This is similar to hyperparameter optimization of the number of neurons (or kernels) in DNN (or CNN).

IV. COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS - TRAINING PHASE

In this section, we carry out a preliminary analysis of the computational complexity of the channel estimation schemes. Specifically, we analyze (i) the total number of trainable parameters in the corresponding NN architectures; and (ii) the size of training dataset required for a target performance.

A. Total Number of Trainable Parameters

The total number of trainable parameters depends on (i) the number of hidden layers in the NN, which is equal to 1 for the shallow 1D-CNN, and 2 for GNN, where the first layer generates the initial estimate, while the second layer performs message passing algorithm (MPA) to aggregate information from one-hop neighbours [13]; (ii) the number of inputs $2N_R N_P$; (iii) the number of neurons at the output layer, which is the total number of real values to be estimated (real and imaginary channel coefficients) $N_L = 2N_T N_R$; (iv) the number of kernels (N_k) and their size which reads $k_h \times k_w$, for CNNs; and (v) the number of node/edge features (d_l) in the GNN. In CNNs, the number of kernels has a significant impact on the prediction performance. Having considered all of the above variables, the number of trainable parameters for the NN architectures can be computed as shown in Table I.

TABLE I
NUMBER OF TRAINABLE PARAMETERS FOR THE DIFFERENT NEURAL NETWORK ARCHITECTURES.

1D-CNN	$N_k(N_{ch}k_hk_w + 1) + 2(L - 1)N_RN_T(N_kN_P + 1)$
GNN	$d_l(N_RN_T + 1) + 2N_RN_T(d_lN_RN_P + 1)$

Fig. 3. Total number of trainable parameters for different neural network schemes and MIMO configurations. The architectures are tuned for optimal MSE performance at 20dB SNR.

Complementarily, Fig. 3 shows the total number of trainable parameters needed for the various NN architectures and across different MIMO configurations. For 1D-CNN, we force the number of kernels to be the lowest possible such that the NN-based estimator outperforms the LS/u-MMSE benchmark in terms of normalized MSE. The kernel size for 1D-CNN is set to $k_h \times k_w = N_R \times 2$, owing to the input shape of received signal at the receiver [7] (real and imaginary parts stacked column-wise).

The figure reveals that 1D-CNN employs a higher number of trainable parameters than that of GNNs. The difference in the number of trainable parameters required increases as the MIMO system scales up. For 16×16 configuration, 1D-CNNs require more than $100\times$ the number of trainable parameters² than GNNs. This stark difference is because in GNNs, the same weights (W_{edge}, W_t, W_r) are used for each edge to compute the channel coefficients, unlike 1D-CNN which demands higher number of kernels as the MIMO system scales up. This shows that GNNs are scalable architectures.

The number of trainable parameters has a direct impact on the computational complexity of both the training and prediction phases. A more detailed analysis of computational complexity in the *prediction* phase in terms of the number of additions and multiplications needed is carried out in Section V ahead.

B. Size of the Training Dataset Required

In the training phase, the computational complexity depends on (i) the number of trainable parameters (previous section); (ii) the number of epochs needed for reaching convergence/stability; and (iii) the number of examples in the training dataset processed in each epoch.

²Note that y-axis is in log scale.

Fig. 4. Channel estimation performance versus training dataset size for a total of 100 training epochs at 20dB for different MIMO configurations (4×4 left, 16×16 right).

Concerning (ii) and (iii), Fig. 4 depicts the estimation error as a function of the number of examples in the training dataset. The different NNs are trained for a total of 100 epochs to ensure training convergence. Performance is given in terms of *normalized* MSE, relative to the number of channel coefficients to be estimated. Fig. 4 reveals that the number of examples required for training different neural networks depends on the MIMO configuration: the higher the number of antennas (sub-plot on the right), the more examples are needed for a target NMSE.

For both MIMO configurations, the GNN architectures reach convergence faster than 1D-CNNs. For 4×4 MIMO, both architectures require at least 5,000 samples to achieve optimum performance. Interestingly, for 16×16 MIMO settings, GNN maintains the rate of convergence, whereas 1D-CNN exhibits much slower convergence. Additionally, at 20dB, 1D-CNNs reach an NMSE error floor which is slightly higher than that of GNNs. Thus, at higher configurations, 1D-CNNs demand a larger training dataset to reach convergence. In the light of the above, for the simulation results in Section V, a training dataset with $M = 10^4$ examples will be used since this guarantees the best performance (lowest NMSE) for all the NN architectures under consideration.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

Here, we assess the performance of the proposed channel estimation schemes by showing results for four different scenarios comprising a MIMO system with $N_T = N_R = 2, 4, 8, 16$ transmit and receive antennas, respectively. The transmit and receive correlation coefficient of the correlation matrices \mathbf{C}_{T_x} and \mathbf{C}_{R_x} are chosen as Toeplitz matrices with values in the n -th diagonal set to $0.9^{|n|}$. The GNN models have been implemented using PyTorch Geometric library [15], which is specifically built to easily code and train GNNs, while the 1D-CNNs are coded using PyTorch. The dataset (generated using Sionna [16]) has a total of $M = 10^4$ examples, each comprising $N_P = N_T$ pilot symbols since this is the minimum number of symbols required to render the problem solvable in the case of linear channel estimators (e.g., LS, MMSE).

A. Channel Estimation Performance

The architecture of the 1D-CNN comprises $L = 1$ hidden layer with a varying number of kernels N_k that depends on the

corresponding MIMO configuration (as discussed in [7]). The input to the 1D-CNN is reshaped to a $N_R \times 2N_P$ matrix. The kernels are of size $k_h \times k_w = N_T \times 2$ which take strides of 2 along the dimensions of the input [7]. For the GNN models, we set the number of edge features d_l in the hidden layers to 4, after performing hyperparameter tuning in the range of [2, 4, 8]. A different model is fit for each SNR in the range of -10 dB to 20 dB. For the stochastic adaptive gradient descent algorithm (Adagrad), the learning rate is set to 0.01, and a batch size of 64 samples is used for the computation of the gradient for all the neural networks. The models are trained for 100 epochs to ensure convergence. All the aforementioned parameters are optimized via grid search. As benchmarks, we use the linear Least Squares (LS) estimator, the (optimal) MMSE estimator with knowledge of the spatial covariance matrices, and the (sub-optimal) u-MMSE channel estimator given by equations (2), (3), and (4), respectively; the shallow 1D-CNN benchmark is from our previous work [7].

The NMSE performance as a function of the SNR is depicted in Fig. 5 (for smaller MIMO settings) and Fig. 6 (larger ones). The proposed GNN outperforms the LS and u-MMSE benchmarks in all MIMO settings. For the case of 4×4 MIMO, the channel estimation improvement with respect to LS is one order of magnitude at 0dB. The performance of GNN is similar to that of the shallow 1D-CNN architecture. They are identical to that of the optimal MMSE estimator (lower bound) in the low- and mid-SNR regimes; and arbitrarily close to optimal MMSE in the high SNR regime. It should be noted that the MMSE benchmark is assumed to have complete knowledge of the correlation matrices, while the NNs leverage on the channel statistics learnt during the training phase. GNNs achieve similar performance to 1D-CNNs with lesser number of training parameters, as discussed in Section IV-A.

At higher MIMO configurations (Fig. 6), the channel estimation gains by NNs continue to outperform the linear benchmarks in the low-SNR regime. The figure reveals that for 16×16 MIMO scenario, the gap of shallow 1D-CNN and GNN with respect to the lower-bound benchmark is more noticeable. At high SNR, 1D-CNN exhibits a flat NMSE behaviour, while GNN offers substantially better performance. This is attributed to the message passing algorithm which refines the channel estimate in GNN.

B. Complexity Analysis - Prediction Phase

In the *prediction* phase, computational complexity of neural networks is determined by the number of operations performed in the forward pass. Figure 7 shows the number of operations (multiplications and additions) carried out by each of the neural network architectures, compared with the linear benchmarks based on the formulae in Table II. The figure (y-axis in log scale) shows that for a given MIMO system, GNN-based estimators require at least $10 \times$ more multiplication and $100 \times$ more addition operations than those of LS/u-MMSE estimators. GNNs record a higher number of additions than 1D-CNNs (owing to the message passing algorithm). However, at higher MIMO settings, the total number of operations

Fig. 5. Estimation error for LS, MMSE, u-MMSE and various NN-based channel estimators for smaller MIMO settings (2×2 , 4×4). The architectures are tuned for optimized MSE performance at 20dB SNR.

shown in Figure 8 reveals that GNNs require lesser number of operations than 1D-CNN models.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have investigated the use of graph neural networks for MIMO channel estimation. Its performance-complexity trade-off is analyzed with respect to that of shallow 1D-CNNs which in our previous works had been shown to outperform shallow (and deep) DNNs and 2D-CNNs. GNN architectures offer similar channel estimation performance to that of the 1D-CNN. When compared with classical channel estimation strategies (LS, MMSE), GNNs are able to reduce channel estimation errors by several orders of magnitude. The computational complexity of GNN in terms of the number of trainable parameters is significantly lower than 1D-CNN across all MIMO configurations. The number of additions/multiplications needed in the the inference phase of GNN is lower than 1D-CNN for large MIMO configurations.

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TABLE II
COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY OF DIFFERENT CHANNEL ESTIMATION SCHEMES IN THE PREDICTION PHASE.

Variable	LS/MMSE	1D-CNN	GNN
Number of multiplications in forward pass	$N_R^2 N_P$	$N_{ch} N_k k_h k_w + 2N_k N_P N_T N_R$	$N_T N_R N_P (6d_l + (L - 2)3d_l^2 + 6d_l)$
Number of additions in forward pass	$N_R^2 (N_P - 1)$	$N_k N_{ch} (k_h k_w - 1) + 2N_R N_T$	$N_T N_R (5d_l + 2(N_T + N_R - 2) + 6d_l - 2) + N_R N_T (L - 2)(3d_l^2 - d_l + d_l(N_T + N_R - 2))$

Fig. 6. Estimation error for LS, MMSE, u-MMSE, and various NN-based channel estimators for larger MIMO settings (8×8 , 16×16). The architectures are tuned for optimized MSE performance at 20dB SNR.

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Fig. 7. Number of operations (multiplications and additions) for the LS, MMSE, and NN-based channel estimators.

Fig. 8. Total number of operations for the LS, MMSE, and NN-based channel estimators.

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